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MODERATING EFFECT OF BOARD SIZE ON FIRM LEVERAGE AND FINANCIAL REPORTING OF QUOTED NIGERIAN INSURANCE COMPANIES

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Abstract

This study analyzes the moderating effect of board size on firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of quoted Nigerian insurance companies from 2009-2021. The data were sourced from the financial statements of the sampled 15 companies. The dependent variable (financial reporting timeliness) was represented by audit report lag (ADL), while, the independent variable (Firm leverage) was proxied by debt-equity ratio. The analysis was conducted with the aid of STATA 15 econometric software. The data were analyzed by Robust regression techniques using a bi-model approach. The estimation result from model I revealed that firm leverage has a significant positive relationship with audit reports lag, while the model II result showed that board size has an insignificant negative moderating effect on the relationship between firm leverage and audit reports lag. This study recommended that management should discourage high leverage as this has the potential of causing delay in releasing audit reports as there is always procrastinating in reporting bad news.

INTRODUCTION

Financial reporting is concerned with the provision of information which possesses the characteristics of relevance, adequate, comparable and reliable sources. Stewardship accounting is achieved through corporate financial reporting in the form of preparation and presentation of audited annual reports and accounts to users of financial information. Financial reports are statements prepared by a company's management to present the financial performance and position at a point in time. These statements are prepared to give users outside of the company, like investors and creditors, more information about company's financial positions. Akle (2011) stated that timeliness of financial is all about

financial statements been published for stakeholders' use when they need them to make decisions, because information loses its usefulness if it is not available when needed. [Emeh & Appah \(2013\)](#) argued that financial information has to be made available in a timely manner so that the users can have access to it whenever they are in a position to make decision and avoid insider trading.

The Securities and Exchange Commission (SEC) which is the regulatory agency of Nigeria Stock Market sets March 31 for every listed firm to submit its audited financial reports ended on December 31 in the previous year. Other Nigerian regulators such as the Investment and Security Act and Insurance Act require a financial statement to be made available on or before 90 days and 180 days post accounting year end respectively ([Iyoha, 2012](#)). [Ibadin & Afensimi \(2015\)](#) point out that Section 347 of the Companies and Allied Matters Act of 2004 as amended, grants an additional 14 days period of grace to companies (in addition to the 90 and 180 days) for their financial statements to be delayed.

Leverage ratios also referred to as gearing ratios are financial ratios that show the percentage of a company's capital structure that is made up on debt or liabilities owed to external creditors ([Fatmawati & Siti, 2023](#)). Focusing on the long-term solvency in general, the more leveraged and higher amount of debt financing relative to equity financing, the owner faces then greater is the risk ([Hendi, 2023](#)). Besides higher leverage is usually associated with higher expected returns. The most common financial leverage ratios are the total debt ratios, the debt/equity ratio, the long-term debt ratio, the time's interest earned ratio, the fixed charge coverage ratio, and the cash coverage ratio.

Board size refers to the number of directors appointed to serve on a company board of directors and there is no regulation that gives specific number of persons that should be appointed to the board. Section 2.1 of the Nigerian [Code of Corporate Governance \(2018\)](#) stipulates that the Board should be of a sufficient size to effectively undertake and fulfil its business; to oversee, monitor, direct and control the company's activities and be relative to the scale and complexity of its operations. The Nigerian [Code of Corporate Governance \(2016\)](#), however, in section 5.4 prescribes an optimum board size of a minimum of 8 for quoted companies, banks and financial institutions in Nigeria. A variable is regarded as a moderator if the relationship between two (or more) other variables is a function of the level of that variable as asserted by [Hair et al. \(1998\)](#). Moderating effect occurs when a third variable changes the relationship between two related variables. In this study board size is used as the moderating variable in the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness since board members bring in their resources in diverse ways to help the company to grow.

In Nigeria, the [Insurance Act \(2003\)](#) provides for the establishment of the National Insurance Commission (NAICOM) as the apex regulator of the insurance industry. The Act stipulates provisions for the subsector which include audit and publication of financial statements. The contribution of the insurance companies to the economic development derived from the risk transfer and indemnification for companies and individuals ([Ene & Bello, 2016](#)). Insurance firms must also comply with the financial reporting requirements as enshrined in the Companies and Allied Matters Act (2004) as amended and other regulations of the Nigerian Exchange Group (NGX).

The paucity of studies that investigated the moderating effect of board size on the relationship between Firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness, more especially of

Nigerian Insurance Companies. Such is a vacuum this study fills with empirical evidence. Secondly, from available literature, there are still mixed findings on the effect of firm leverage on financial reporting timeliness among scholars. For instance, while [Hendi \(2023\)](#); [Efobi and Okougbo \(2014\)](#) documented a significant relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness, [Fatmawati and Siti \(2023\)](#); [Aigienohuwa and Ezejiofor \(2021\)](#) observed that firm leverage has no significant effect on financial reporting timeliness. Furthermore, this study by covering a thirteen (13) year period fills the vacuum created by the short periods of studies as revealed in [Hendi \(2023\)](#); [Abdullah et al. \(2019\)](#); [Raweh et al. \(2019\)](#) who studied only five years, [Fatmawati and Siti \(2023\)](#); [Mutiara et al. \(2018\)](#); [Ahmad et al. \(2018\)](#); and [Warrad \(2018\)](#) covered only three years each. These are some of the problems that necessitate this study.

The broad objective of this study is to analyse the moderating effect of firm leverage on financial reporting timeliness of quoted insurance companies in Nigeria, while the specific objectives are to:

- i. determine the effect of firm leverage on financial reporting timeliness of Nigerian quoted insurance companies;
- ii. estimate the moderating effect of board size on the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of quoted Nigerian insurance companies;

To achieve the stated objectives, the following two-tailed null hypotheses were formulated for testing.

H₀₁: Firm leverage has no significant effect on financial reporting timeliness of quoted Nigerian insurance companies; and

H₀₂: Board size has no significant moderating effect on the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of quoted Nigerian insurance companies.

CONCEPTUAL FRAMEWORK OF THE STUDY

The conceptual framework of the study is made up of the moderating variable board size (BSZ), the independent variable (firm Leverage: LEV) and the dependent variable (financial reporting timeliness) measured by financial reporting lag (FRL). [Aminu \(2015\)](#) noted that a conceptual framework can be better virtualized through its diagrammatical representation as shown below in figure 1.

Adapted from Fujaria and Islinita (2018)

Firm Leverage and Financial Reporting Timeliness

Leverage also known as gearing, can be described as the component of company(s) capital that is financed through debts. A firm is described as leveraged when it is financed partly by long term debts. Thus, leverage measures the extent of the borrowed finance resources used in a firm ([Alkhatib & Marji, 2012](#)). A high leverage firm is expected to release its annual report faster than a low leverage firm, due to the high monitoring cost associated with a highly leveraged firm. Higher leverage rate means that the company is operating more on borrowed funds, which in itself is bad news, and management would delay such

reports. Management of low leverage firms will usually be happy to quickly release their financial reports (even if they do not make much profit) in order to show that they operated mostly on their own resources (Oshodin & Ikhatua, 2018). The high debt to equity ratio in a company is a reflection of financial difficulties, which as bad news will affect the condition of the company in the public eye and in the opinion of Sasundya *et al.* (2018), will cause delay in the publication of financial reports. Adebayo and Adebisi (2016) observed that a high degree of leverage will make company annual reports to delay due to scrutiny from creditors.

Financial Reports Timeliness

Financial reports timeliness generally refers to the length of time from a company's financial year-end to the date of the auditor's report and thus it is measured as the number of days between a firm's fiscal year-end and the day the Annual General Meeting is held. Harris (2014) stated that, timeliness can be measured as the time between when data is expected and when it is readily available for use. The International Accounting Standard Board (IASB) (2008) defined timeliness as making the financial information available to users on time so as to influence their decision. According to Iskandar and Trisnawati (2010), the time duration to finish an audit is called the audit report lag and will influence the timeliness of the information published in an audited financial report. Oshodin and Ikhatua (2018) described timeliness of a report as an attempt on the part of those preparing a financial statement to make it available quickly before it loses its usefulness for decision making. In other words, timeliness is one of the qualitative characteristics of accounting information that defines the relevance of accounting information (IASB, 2015). This study adopts the definition of timeliness of financial reports as offered by Ibadin and Afensimi (2015) who stated that it refers to the length of time in days from a company's financial year-end to the date of the auditor's report is made public.

Board Size and Financial Reporting Timeliness

Board size can be defined as the total number of the members of a firm's board of directors and is an important corporate characteristic that significantly influence the timeliness of financial reports. Board of directors has the responsibility for monitoring, communication, participation and coordination, all of which has direct bearing on how timely the financial report can be made public after the end of the accounting year. Zailut (2010) stated that, if one or more of the board responsibilities becomes a problem as a result of the large number of members of the board, it can affect the timeliness of financial reporting. Appah & Emeh (2013) noted that board size has shown to be a significant part of the ability of boards to effectively monitor management and to work efficiently together to oversee the running of the firm so as to a timely release of the financial statement after the financial year end. Baatwah *et al.* (2016) assert that larger board's members are more helpful to the companies in terms of sharing knowledge, experience, and ideas which make them more efficient in terms of prompt decision making and therefore will not condone delay in financial reports.

According to Aktas and Kargin (2011), large boards are able to delegate more responsibilities to board committees especially the audit committee which can prevent or limit management from exhibiting opportunistic behaviour and delay financial reports in order to postpone bad news. On a different position however, Hassan (2016) pointed out that as far as timeliness of financial reports is concerned in relation to the size of corporate

boards, larger boards cause delays in financials' and auditors' reports due to wider consultations.

The Theory of Anchorage: The Agency Cost Theory

The agency cost theory was developed by Jensen and Meckling in 1976, and holds that the interests of the owner of business (the principal) and that of the managers (the agent) would usually be at variance as the agent have more information at his disposal when compared with the principal. The theory assumes that in the presence of information asymmetry, the agent is likely to pursue interest that may conflict with that of the principal. Since managers are said to favour perks of office and power, even at the expense of shareholders' interest, they are likely to pursue interests that may hurt their principals (the shareholders). The theory therefore suggests an optimal debt level that would arise as a result of agency cost. The theorists suggested a situation whereby the interest of the managers in the firm should increase in order to be aligning with the owners. The debt level should also be used to motivate or control managers' tendency for extra consumption. The theory also assumes that free cash flow in a firm can be controlled by increasing the managers' stake in the firms or debt in the capital structure thereby reducing the amount of free cash available to managers. This theory was chosen as the theory upon which this study is anchored because, this study found out that debts encourage delay in financial reports.

Empirical Review

[Hendi \(2023\)](#) examined the effect of company and audit characteristics on the timeliness of audit reports. The specific objectives were to find out the effect of debt-equity (leverage), larger audit complexity, firm size, loss and ownership concentration on timeliness of audit reports. The study used a panel regression analysis methodology on 115 Indonesian companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2017-2021. The study revealed that company characteristics have a significant effect on the timeliness of audit reports, as larger audit complexity, firm size, and debt-equity lead to shorter audit delays, while, negative profits and ownership concentration cause longer delays. The study recommended that research can apply more varied measurements to the variables contained in the study.

[Fatmawati and Siti \(2023\)](#) sought evidence about the factors that affect the timeliness of financial reporting of manufacturing companies listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange. The specific objectives were debt to equity ratio, profitability, ownership structure, auditor quality, and auditor turnover. The sample of the study was 100 manufacturing companies that were consistently listed on the Indonesia Stock Exchange from 2015-2017 period which were sampled using the purposive sampling method. The analysis was by logistic regression at a significance level of 5 percent. The results of the study revealed that profitability and ownership structure significantly affect the timeliness of the company's financial reporting, while the debt to equity (leverage ratio), auditor quality, and auditor turnover have no significant effect on the timeliness of financial reporting. The study offered no recommendations.

[Aigienhuwa and Ezejiofor \(2021\)](#) determined the relationship between leverage and timeliness of financial reports in Nigerian quoted companies. The specific objective was to find out how leverage affects timeliness of financial reports. The *ex post facto* research design was adopted for the study. The population of the study consists of 145 quoted companies in Nigeria. The sample size was determined using Taro Yamane method. Data were sourced from the content analysis of annual reports and accounts of the selected

quoted Nigerian companies from the year 2010 to 2019. The panel data regression technique was used to estimate the relationship between the variables with aid of EViews 9.0 software. The outcome of the study revealed that firm leverage has no significant relationship with timeliness of financial reports in Nigerian quoted companies. The study recommended that highly financed by debt companies need more audit effort and time due to their business risk and/or volume of work which may imply that debt holders usually require highly geared companies to report timely and at a certain frequency so as to monitor their interest.

[Adediran et al. \(2019\)](#) investigated the effect of firm characteristics on timeliness of financial reports on Nigerian insurance companies from 2008-2017. The specific objectives were to evaluate the effect of firm size, board size and firm leverage on financial reporting timeliness. The study used secondary data that were sourced from the financial statements of the sampled companies. The data were analysed with the descriptive statistics Pairwise correlation, and ordinary least square (OLS) multiple regression technique. The result revealed that board size has a significant negative effect on audit report delay, while firm size has a significant negative effect on audit report delay. The results further revealed that firm leverage has an insignificant negative effect on audit report delay. The study recommended amongst other things that management of large companies should always ensure that highly qualified personnel are placed at the final accounts section of the parent company and that compilation of financial reports should be gradual and not only towards the accounting year end to avoid unnecessary delay in publication of financial statements.

[Bakare et al. \(2018\)](#) examined the effect of board characteristics on timeliness of financial reporting of listed insurance firms in Nigeria for the period 2011-2016. The specific objectives were to analyse the effect of board size and board meeting on financial reporting timeliness. The study used correlational research design. Data were collected from the published annual financial reports of studied listed insurance firms in Nigeria. The population of the study comprised of the 28 listed insurance firms. The sample size was fifteen (15) listed insurance firms in Nigeria. The data were analysed with the aid of Generalized Least Square multiple regression technique. Using 90 firm-year panelled observations, the result of the random effect showed that board size has a positive and significant effect on the timeliness of financial reporting of listed insurance firms in Nigeria. Also, board meeting has a significant effect on timeliness of financial reporting. The study recommended that the shareholders of listed insurance firms should ensure that the board has a reasonable large number of members as it has been revealed that a larger board will reduce the delay of releasing the financial reports and that the number of meetings held by the directors should be reduced so that the executive directors can focus well on their managerial responsibilities.

[Adebayo and Adebisi \(2016\)](#) investigated the timeliness of financial statements among the deposit money banks in Nigeria. The specific objectives were to find out how bank size, leverage, profitability, audit firm size affect the timeliness of financial statements. A sample of 15 deposit money banks listed by the Nigeria Stock Exchange between 2005 and 2013 were studied. The data were analysed and results estimated using Ordinary Least Square (OLS) regression complimented with the panel data estimation technique. All the variables examined (size, profitability and audit firm size) were found to have significant effect on timeliness of financial reports, except for leverage. The findings also revealed that most of the banks now comply with regulations which enhance timely reporting of financial

statements in Nigeria. The study recommended that the regulatory agencies should not allow the time lag to be too long, so that the report will be useful for the intended purpose.

Ibadin and Afensimi (2015) examine the determinants of audit report lag in the Nigerian context. Specifically, the study examined the effects of leverage, return on equity, firm size, audit fees, audit firm type, subsidiaries and financial year-end on audit reporting timeliness. The panel research design was used for the study. The data were sourced from the annual reports of all financial companies quoted on the floor of the Nigerian stock exchange. The method of data analysis adopted was the panel data estimation techniques (pooled, fixed and random effects regression). The findings revealed that company size has no significant positive impact on audit delay; firm's financial performance has a significant impact on audit delay; audit firm type (big 4 and non-big 4) has a significant impact on audit delay; Leverage has no significant impact on audit delay; number of subsidiaries has a significant impact on audit delay and financial-year end has no significant impact on Audit delay. The study recommended that in achieving the objective of making the financial statements readily available for making timely decisions, the Nigerian stock exchange, Securities and Exchange Commission, the Financial Reporting Council, the Central Bank of Nigeria and other regulatory bodies should put in place measures to ensure strict compliance with 3 months window for financial reports preparation and presentation.

Efobi and Okougbo (2014) explore the factors that can influence the timeliness of financial reporting in Nigeria using a sample of 33 financial institutions (2005-2008). The specific objectives were to establish the impact of size, leverage and performance, age and corporate governance on the financial reporting timeliness. The Generalized Least Square (GLS) regression method was used for the estimation and the results reveal that on the average, the sampled companies used 122 days after the year end for the release of their financial reports. The size, leverage and performance of the companies have a negative significant relationship with the timeliness of their financial reports while the age of the company has a positive significant impact. Corporate governance plays a complementary role with some of the explanatory variables to explain financial reporting timeliness in Nigeria. The study recommended a sound corporate governance practice that can influence corporate attributes to enhance the timeliness of financial reporting.

METHODOLOGY

This study adopts the *ex-post facto* research design because the events under study had taken place and the data are historical in nature. Ex-post facto research design has a very important advance of high verifiability.

The population of the study consists of twenty-three (23) insurance companies quoted on the Nigeria Exchange Group (NGX) as at 31st December, 2021. The study sample size is fifteen (15) of the 23 insurance companies. The sampling technique adopted by this study was purposive sampling method. The panel data used were obtained from the various insurance companies' financial statements. The data were analysed with the aid pooled ordinary least square (OLS) regression technique. The diagnostic tests conducted were Descriptive statistics for means and standard deviations, Ramsey RESET for specifying the appropriateness Pearson correlation, Skewness/Kurtosis for normality and Heteroskedasticity to determine the stability of the residuals.

Variable Measurement and Justification

The variables under study are explained in the Table 1 below.

Table 1: Definition of Variables

Variable	Type	Measurement	Justification
Audit Report (2023); Lag (ARL)	Dependent	Number of days from the accounting -year end to date of AGM.	Hendi (2023); Fatmawati and Siti Adediran <i>et al.</i> (2019)
Firm Leverage (2023); (LEV)	Independent	Percentage of total assets financed by debts.	Hendi (2023); Fatmawati and Siti Aigienohuwa and Ezejiofor (2021)
Board Size (BSZ)	Moderating	Number of Directors on board of companies in a financial year	Adediran <i>et al.</i> (2019); Bakare <i>et al.</i> (2018); Azubike <i>et al.</i> (2014)

Source: Researcher's compilation, 2023

Model Specification

This study adopts a bi-model approach in the model specification for clarity of presentation. The model 1 captures the direct relationship between the independent variables (firm leverage) the moderating variable (board size) and the dependent variable (audit report lag) without effecting the moderation.

The specified linear equation for model I as used by [Ahmad et al. \(2018\)](#) is as follows:

$$ARL = f(LEV + BSZ).$$

Econometrically, the above relationship is represented below:

$$ARL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1LEV_{it} + \beta_2BSZ_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots (Model I)$$

Model II captures the indirect relationship between the independent and dependent variable moderated by board size. The specified linear relationship is presented in the equation below:

$$ARL = f (LEV + LEV*BSZ).$$

In econometric terms, the above equation is rewritten as:

$$ARL_{it} = \beta_0 + \beta_1LEV_{it} + \beta_2LEV*BSZ_{it} + \mu_{it} \dots\dots\dots (Model II)$$

Where:

ARL = an indicator for audit report lag (a proxy for financial reporting timeliness);

β_0 = Intercept term (a constant);

β_1 = Coefficient of Board Size;

β_2 = Coefficient of Board Size-moderated Leverage.

LEV = a predictor for Firm Leverage;

BSZ = a predictor for Board Size (The moderating variable);

BSZ*LEV = a predictor for Board Size-moderated Firm Leverage.

μ = Stochastic error term;

i = Firms;

t = Periods; and

f = Functional relationship.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Descriptive Statistics

Table 2 shows the descriptive statistics of the variables which summarized the distribution pattern of the dataset.

Table 2: Descriptive Statistics

Variable	Obs	Mean	Std. Dev.	Min	Max
ARL	195	202.892	115.687	51	767
LEV	195	1.026	1.812	-6.74	15.11
BSZ	195	10.605	2.442	6	17

Source: STATA software output, 2021

Table 2 above revealed that audit report lag (ADL) had a mean value of 202.89 which serves as the average of the number of days the sampled insurance companies hold their AGMs. The ADL had a minimum of 51 days and a maximum of 767 days. This result signifies that most of the samples companies exceeded the 180 days stipulated by legislation. Results from Table 2 above showed that all the three variables have mean values which lie within the range of the minimum and maximum between their respective minimum and maximum values, which according to Ifarajimi and Ola (2017) is evidence of the fact that the data distribution evenly spread. Table 2 also revealed the standard deviation which describes the extent of dispersion from the central mean for ARL and BSZ (2.227 & 2.442) are lower than their means (2.247 & 10.605 respectively), which implies that ARL and BSZ were less widely dispersed and therefore has a slower growth rate. LEV on the other hand, had a standard deviation (1.812) that is greater than its mean (1.026) indicating that LEV was more widely dispersed from its mean and so has a faster growth rate.

Correlation Matrix for Multicollinearity

Table 3 below shows the results of the Pearson correlation matrix which tested the strength of the relationship between the independent variables. The decision rule is to recognize the presence of multicollinearity if any two independent variables correlate above 0.85 or conclude that multicollinearity does not exist if no two-pair correlate to the stated threshold.

Table 3: Multicollinearity Test

	ARL	LEV	BSZ
ARL	1.000		
LEV	0.038	1.000	
BSZ	-0.084	0.232	1.000

Source: STATA 12 output, 2023

Results from Table 3 above revealed that no pair of the independent variables correlate up to the level stipulated by Hair *et al* (2005), in fact the correlation the LEV and BSZ is 0.232 (23%). This result indicates that there is no multicollinearity within the models.

Shapiro-Wilk W' Data Normality Test

Table 4 below presents the Shapiro-Wilk normality test which is concerned with determining whether a data residual is normally distributed not. The decision rule is that any model with a p-value that is less than or equal to 0.05 has residuals that were not normally distributed, while, a p-value higher than 0.05 indicates normally distribution of residuals.

Table 4: Shapiro-Wilk W Test for Normal Data

Variable	Obs	W	V	z	Prob>z
residual	195	0.3969	88.014	10.289	0.000

Source: STATA output, 2023

Table 4 above revealed that the models have residuals that were not normally distributed. This finding forecloses the chance of estimating the model with Ordinary Least Squares regression which assumes that all data are normally distributed. The Robust regression which is less affected by data with such an unusual feature is best for estimating the models (Kutner *et al.* 2004)

Ramsey RESET (Omitted Variable Test (ovt))

Table 5 below shows the Ramsey Regression Equation Specification Error Test (RESET) conducted for omitted variables. The decision rule is that if the p-value is greater than 0.05 (insignificant), the model has no omitted variables and the functional forms as specified are correct, while, a p-value lower than or equals to 0.05, indicates that there are omitted variables

Table 5: Ramsey RESET

Ramsey RESET test using powers of the fitted values of arl

Ho: model has no omitted variables

F(3, 149) = 19.51

Prob > F = 0.0241

Source: STATA output, 2023.

Table 5 above revealed a p-value of 0.0241 which is less than 0.05 indicating that the Null hypothesis which states that the model has no omitted variables is rejected. This finding implies that there are omissions of any variables which could have altered the results obtained.

Regression Analysis (Model I)

The first model involves the direct relationship between the independent variables and the dependent variable without the moderator. The result of this model was used to test hypothesis one.

Table 6: Model I Regression

I_arl	Robust			P> z
	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	
LEV	0.1806	0.0674	2.68	0.022**
BSZ	-0.0083	0.0099	-0.84	0.666
_cons	0.1057	0.1016	1.04	0.472

R-squared Overall = 0.3362
Wald chi² = 19.47
Prob > chi² = 0.0102

*Note: ** = 5% significant level.*

Source: STATA output, 2023.

Table 6 above showed coefficient of determination (R-square overall) which measured the combined effects of LEV and BSZ (both regressed as independent variables) on the dependent variable (ARL) was 0.3362, which implies that about 33% of the variations in the financial reporting timeliness of the sampled insurance companies from 2009-2021 was as a result of LEV and BSZ during the period studied. Table 6 also revealed a Wald chi² of 19.47 and a prob>chi² of 0.0102 which indicate that the model is fit.

Regression Analysis (Model II)

The second model of the regression analysis involves the indirect relationship between the independent variable (LEV) and the dependent variable (ARL) moderated by BSZ is presented in Table 7 below. The result obtained from the model II was used to test hypothesis two.

Table 7: Model II Regression Analysis

	Robust			
I_ard	Coef.	Std. Err.	z	P> z
LEV	0.0132	0.0394	0.34	0.737
BSZ_LEV	-0.0002	0.0031	-0.07	0.945
_cons	0.0212	0.0316	0.67	0.712
R-squared Overall = 0.3109				
Wald chi ² (9) = 16.42				
Prob > chi ² = 0.003				

Source: STATA output, 2023.

Table 7 above revealed a coefficient of determination (R-squared overall) also called Goodness of fit of 0.3109, indicating that the independent variable (LEV) and board size - moderated LEV exerted approximately 31% influence on the changes experienced in the financial reporting timeliness of the Nigerian insurance companies studied from 2009-2021. The results also revealed a Wald chi² of 16.42 and a p-value of 0.003 (significant at 1% level), both indicating that the model is fit.

Test of Hypotheses

Hypothesis One

Firm Leverage has no significant relationship with financial reporting timeliness of quoted Nigerian insurance companies.

Table 6 above revealed that leverage (LEV) has a significant (0.022) positive (2.68) relationship with financial reporting timeliness proxied by audit report lag (ADL) of insurance companies in Nigeria from 2009-2021, which implies that the two-tailed null hypothesis one (H₀₁) is rejected.

Hypothesis Two

Board size has no significant moderating effect on firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of quoted insurance companies in Nigeria.

-0.0002 0.0031 -0.07 0.945

Table 7 above showed that board size (BSZ) has an insignificant (0.945) negative moderating (-0.07) effect on the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of the Nigerian insurance companies from 2009-2021. This result indicated that the formulated null hypothesis two (H₂) is accepted. Comparing results from both models I and II, it is clear that firm leverage has a significant positive relationship with audit report lag in model I, but when moderated by board size, leverage has an insignificant negative relationship with audit report lag.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Table 6 above further revealed that firm leverage (LEV) has a significant positive relationship with audit report lag (ADL) which proxied financial reporting timeliness with a coefficient of 0.1806, a z-statistic of 2.68 and a p-value of 0.022 from 2009-2021. This finding means that in the absence of any other variables, a unit increase in the debt-equity ratio of the firm will lead to a significant increase in the delay in releasing audit reports. This

finding corroborates those of Hendi (2023); Efobi and Okuogbo (2014) who reported that firm leverage has a significant relationship with financial reporting timeliness. The finding, however, is at variance with those of Fatmawati and Siti (2023); Adediran *et al.* (2019), Adebayo and Adebisi (2016) who observed that firm leverage has an insignificant relationship with financial reporting timeliness.

Table 7 above indicated that board size has an insignificant (0.945) negative (-0.07) moderating effect on the relationship between firm leverage and audit report lag of Nigerian insurance companies with a coefficient of -0.0002 from 2009-2021. This finding signifies that board size is not a strong moderating variable in investigating the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting timeliness of Nigerian insurance companies.

CONCLUSION AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Arising from the findings of this study, the following conclusions were drawn.

- i. A highly leveraged company is likely to publish its audit report very late because of trying to find excuses for employing high debts and also to delay bad news.
- ii. In analyzing the effect of a third variable on the relationship between firm leverage and financial reporting, board size is a weak moderating variable.

Based on the findings of this study, the following recommendations were made:

- i. Insurance companies in Nigeria should discourage high debt-equity ratio as this has the potential of causing delay in releasing audit reports as management may be not motivated to report bad news.
- ii. In determining the effect of firm leverage on financial report timeliness, board size should not be considered as a useful moderating variable as it has an insignificant effect in the relationship.

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